

TRAINING PSYCHOLOGIST-TRAINERS TO IMPROVE THEIR SKILLS AND ORGANIZE PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAININGS

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Abstract. *This study provides recommendations for improving the professional skills of psychologist-trainers and using methods for organizing psychological trainings for psychologist-trainers. Information is provided on conducting psychological trainings in higher educational institutions, the role of trainings in human life, the importance of the training process in the formation of skills and abilities to solve problems that may arise in a person, the organization of psychological trainings, training stages, training goals, and laws that must be followed during the training process.*

Keywords: *Psychological research, psychologist-trainer, professional skills, training rules, psychological training.*

ПОДГОТОВКА ПСИХОЛОГОВ-ТРЕНЕРОВ ДЛЯ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ КВАЛИФИКАЦИИ И ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ТРЕНИНГОВ

Аннотация. *В исследовании даны рекомендации по повышению профессионального мастерства психологов-тренеров и по повышению профессионального мастерства психологов-тренеров посредством использования методов организации психологического обучения. Приведена информация о проведении психологического обучения в высших учебных заведениях, роли обучения в жизни человека, значении процесса обучения в формировании навыков и умений решать проблемы, которые могут возникнуть у человека, организации психологического обучения, этапах обучения, целях обучения, законах, которые необходимо соблюдать в процессе обучения.*

Ключевые слова: *Психологическое исследование, психолог-тренер, профессиональные навыки, правила обучения, психологический тренинг.*

PSIXOLOG-TRENERLARNI MALAKASINI OSHIRISH VA PSIXOLOGIK TRENINGLARNI TASHKILLASHTIRISHGA TAYYORLASH

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot psixolog-trenerlarning kasbiy malakasini oshirish va psixolog-trenerlarga psixologik treninglarni tashkillashtirishda metodlardan foydalanish orqali kasbiy ko'nikmalarini oshirishga tavsiyalar beramiz. Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida psixologik treninglarni o'tkazish, inson hayotida treninglarni o'rni, shaxsda vujudga kelishi mumkin bo'lgan muammolarni yechish uchun malaka va ko'nikmalarning hosil bo'lishida trening jarayoni ahamiyati, psixologik treninglarni tashkil etish, trening bosqichlari, trening maqsadlari, trening jarayonida amal qilinishi lozim bo'lgan qonunlar to'g'risida ma'mulotlar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Psixologik tadqiqotlar, psixolog-trener, kasbiy mahorat, trening qoidalari, psixologik treninglar.

Introduction

One of the problems of modern psychology is the upbringing of well-rounded individuals, their help in finding their place in society, and the development of their skills. In our country, increasing the activity of young people and creating all the conditions for their formation as well-rounded individuals is considered a priority direction of state policy. The Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 sets out such important goals as "...to educate young people as individuals with firm beliefs and views on life..."¹. This goal involves the development of measures to improve the overall health of young people, as well as to provide them with the skills and abilities to solve problems that may arise throughout their lives. In recent years, the problem of human health has become not only physical, but also spiritual and mental health, and in such circumstances, the demand for psychological training, which is widely used in modern psychology, is increasing. Training is taken from English and means "to practice", "to repeat".

When it comes to psychological training, this term is perceived by many as "a training in which solutions to problems are found". In fact, training sessions do not solve people's problems, but rather develop the skills and competencies necessary to analyze the root of these problems. TRAINING is a training session conducted through various games and exercises in order to develop the skills and competencies necessary to solve existing or potential problems in a person.

Although different authors have different approaches to defining or explaining training, most of them focus on the fact that training sessions are carried out through games and exercises and that skills and competencies are developed during the training process. Any training begins with setting a goal.

The work carried out by the trainer, preparing the group for training and conducting the training session are all formed and developed around the initially set goal. Therefore, the more clearly the initial goal is formulated, the more clearly it is delivered and accepted by all participants - this is what determines the high level of success achieved in the training. It is precisely the proportion of the achieved success to the goal that experts emphasize, 90% of success depends on how clearly the goal is formulated. It is advisable to organize training groups to deal with people who have applied for specific psychological problems, and to organize individual conversations with them. Because knowing the identity of the group participants, their character traits allows the trainer to draw a certain conclusion about the group as a whole. This is useful when drawing up a program and plan for the training session, and choosing the methods to be used during the training process. In addition, it is also necessary for the trainer to know the motivation of each participant well, otherwise they may leave the group. This will negatively affect the effectiveness of the training. To ensure the effectiveness of training sessions, it is necessary to pay attention to several important aspects when organizing them. In the process of preparing for and conducting a training session, the trainer should take into account the following important aspects: The duration of training sessions should be as follows: 1. 4-5 days a week, 8 hours a day (with a 30 or 60 minute break). This is the most effective training session. 2. 2-3 days a week, 4-5 hours a day. It gives an average effective result. 3. 1 day a week, 3-4 hours a day. Training sessions organized with such a duration are expected to be less effective. The room where the training will be held. One of the factors ensuring the effectiveness of the training is the presence of all the necessary conditions in the room so that each participant feels comfortable. Taking this into account, it is recommended that the training room be comfortable, spacious, designed for free movement, and equipped with the necessary equipment. Group norms should be developed in cooperation with the trainer and the group participants. When developing group norms, it is advisable for the trainer to collect ideas using the "Brainstorming" method. It is advisable for the group members themselves to give suggestions and opinions on what rules should be followed during the training process, and it is advisable for the participant who gives a certain opinion to explain the importance of this opinion for the training, after which the participants and his proposal are accepted or rejected. Training rules or laws serve to control and regulate the processes within the group. The application of these laws will be a help for the training participants, and on the contrary, if the trainer does not pay attention to them, the training group may "split" or "injure" the participants. The following laws must be followed in any training: One of the main parts that should be carried out on the first day of the training session is the introduction of group members to each other and to the trainers.

This part is carried out through various games proposed by the trainer. Therefore, the introduction can be organized in different ways, but the essence of the introduction part is the same: each participant can introduce themselves in the way they want others to recognize them or call them in the group. After the introduction, the trainer asks each group member what they expect from the training. The important aspect of this part is that, along with giving the participant an initial incentive to talk about their problem, the trainer can make changes to his program and plan accordingly after learning their expectations. During the expectation-setting phase, the group members are asked to sit in a circle and express their expectations from the training, any concerns they have, or any objections they have about the aspects they do not like. The trainer should listen to all participants' opinions with empathy, without judging, discussing, or being surprised, and thank each participant for sharing their box with others. In order to achieve effectiveness in conducting any training sessions, it is first necessary to create an atmosphere of sincerity, openness, and mutual trust among the participants. Without these, the intended goal of the training cannot be achieved. Creating such an atmosphere requires great skill from the facilitator, and also depends on the methods used in the training process. Such methods include those called "non-traditional methods of education" and have become widely used in our education system.

Conclusion

Psychological training is entering various areas of social practice to solve the problem of achieving healthy relationships between people. Its diagnostic analysis and psychocorrectional capabilities have an effective impact on the work of personnel: specialists, psychologists, teachers, psychotherapists, managers of enterprises and organizations, entrepreneurs. At the same time, it also imposes a high task on the fields of psychology to educate young people who are in line with the requirements of the times, think deeply, influence the social environment through their rational thinking in various situations, and have a broad worldview. After all, the subject of psychological training in our national psychology is the most effective and modern solution.

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